

Soils Research and Irrigation in Canterbury

One day Regional Workshop

Lincoln, New Zealand
March 2012

These proceedings are intended to recover useful information and insights from Workshops in a manner that is faithful to the intent, and in an open and readily accessible manner. Frequently, Workshops of this nature present current information not otherwise published and therefore hard or impossible to find later.

Other Proceedings already available

Celebrating Soils in the Hub: Workshop (Nov 2015) <https://zenodo.org/communities/nzsss2015>

Animal Supplementary Feed Workshop (Dec 2017) <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1305420>

Presentations and Notes
from the
Soils Research and Irrigation in Canterbury
One day Regional Workshop

Lincoln, New Zealand

March 2012

The workshop was planned and organised by:

Dr Trish Fraser, The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited

With thanks to NZSSS for funding, and other support from:

Profitability. Sustainability. Competitiveness.

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Rainshelter facility at Plant & Food Research, Lincoln showing cereals under different irrigation treatments.

Foreword

Long term Canterbury rainfall average appears nearly even throughout the year, but in practice each year there is a marked dry period at some stage Figure 1. Plants respond to actual rainfall rather than the long term mean, or “plants grow in real weather, not average weather”.

Irrigation is a vital component to security of yield in such a variable climate, whether the plant is the final harvest or as animal feed/pasture. Since this Workshop in 2012, significant increases in Canterbury land area under irrigation have occurred, not least the [Central Plains Water](#) scheme. Drought conditions illustrate the value not only of irrigation as a distribution mechanism, but also of storage of water through and between seasons.

Figure 1 Canterbury (Broadfields station) long term mean monthly rainfall with a few selected years. Note the sometimes extreme variation from long term average for various months, but different in each year.

Soil types and management are another major component of plant production. Increased irrigation capacity requires an increase in value derived from this land. Almost inevitably, this occurs as increased intensification of land use. This intensification commonly also means a greater demand overall for water supply, as well as the risk of greater losses to the environment. Water losses, whether overland or to aquifers, inevitably carries sediments and nutrients. Intensified animal production suggests an increase in animal wastes needing management and treatment/disposal, including for pathogen management. However, there is also a view that intensification provides environmental benefits (Phalan et al. 2016; Balmford et al. 2018).

In the intervening years, considerable progress has been made towards managing and mitigating losses from intensive agriculture on the typically shallow, stony and free draining soils of the Canterbury plains. Nitrate leaching has been a particular focus, with participation in the development of good management practices ([GMP](#)), plus numerous examples of better matching crop uptake to supply.

Warrick Nelson, October 2018

References

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WORKSHOP PRESENTATIONS

Introduction: Trish Fraser

"Soil Research and Irrigation in Canterbury"

NZSSS Workshop at Lincoln
1st March 2012

Introductory challenge:
As a table group work out...

If you had \$500,000 to invest in Canterbury soils and irrigation research ...

What research question would you allocate it to?

Session I

How can we tailor irrigation schemes to land/soil resources?

Research Stocktake Framework

How can we tailor irrigation schemes to land/soil resources?

Session II

Do we have the knowhow to conduct on-farm irrigation sustainably?

Research Stocktake Framework

Do we have the knowhow to conduct on-farm irrigation sustainably?

Research Stocktake Framework

Do we understand the soil processes to allow sustainable land management under irrigation?

Session III

Do we understand the soil processes to allow sustainable land management under irrigation?

Acknowledgements

- Presenters
- Facilitator: Ian Tarbotton provided by:

- Funder: NZ Society of Soil Science

- Initiators: Team from

Session I - How can we tailor irrigation schemes to land/soil resources?

Overview/ where soil research fits in irrigation expansion? Murray Doak

Soil – the make or break point for irrigation development?

Soils research and irrigation workshop
1 March 2012

Murray Doak
MAF Irrigation Acceleration Fund

Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry
Te Minita Rauwhenua Tapunui

BIOSSECURITY NEW ZEALAND Fisheries NZPAC MAF

Government direction on irrigation

- Currently about 620,000ha irrigated, \$1b+ GDP
- NZIER – 347,000ha new irrigation lifts exports \$4b
- Production increase, economic diversity, buffer shocks

- Economic growth and environmental outcomes
- “best value for society”

- 2011 NPS - IAF – Clean-up Fund - initial linked policies
- Current LaWF – further policy improvements

Irrigation Acceleration Fund

- Easy water allocated, but sub-optimally used
- Collective funding challenges, collaborative, integrated, commercially viable, robustly conceived and governed
- Lever to improve use and management of water resources
 - Reliability
 - Managing to limits
 - Accountability - good practice, ASM
- \$35m over 5 years to assist strategies and specific proposals to investment ready stage

What does this mean for soils research?

Basis for managing intensification – **soil determines outcomes = investment return**

4 dimensions of soil information needed

- **Resource policy and management**
 - Spatial planning, models, climate variability, NZ and global context
- **Land/farm management**
 - Good practice, crop growth models, externalities, tools, systems approaches, extension/participation
- **Physical properties**
 - water use efficiency, infiltration, precision
- **Chemical and biological properties**
 - Nutrient behaviour, fertiliser, effluent, additives

What DO we know and what DON'T we know within each of these dimensions??

Soil natural capital and soil services of irrigable land. Allan Hewitt

Soil natural capital and soil services of irrigable land

Allan Hewitt LCR
 Estelle Dominate AgR
 Trevor Webb LCR
 Carolyn Hedley LCR

In economic analyses - the soil has been set aside as an "externality"

In response, Natural Capital concept attempts to integrate thinking about economics and ecology (incl. soil) by conceiving 'nature' as 'capital' (Brent Clothier)

Our challenge then: how to express what soil is & does for us by measures of value - that will bring soil into the economic equation?

Sustainable Land Use Research Initiative
 Plant and Food
 AgResearch
 Landcare Research

We build on prior work in SLURI (incl. Estelle Dominati's PhD)

- Framework for Soil Natural Capital and Soil Services
- Estimating soil services values (intensive dairy soil - Waikato)
 - **Provisioning soil services**
 e.g. pasture quantity, pasture quality, animal support ...
 - **Regulating soil services**
 e.g. N filtering, NO₂ regulation, CH₄ regulation, Flood mitigation ...

Dominati Estelle, Patterson Murray, Mackay, Alec

Develop this by work by quantifying Soil Nat Cap and Soil Services for irrigated dairy on a range of Canterbury soils

Stock adequacy method to quantify soil natural capital

Goals: Refine SNC/ soil service value estimates, learn how to use them to support decision making

Q? What are the true comparative values of soils – for a specific use?

Q? How to use soil service values to analyse trade-offs between:
 Soil ↔ Water ↔ Profit ↔ Off-site environ.

Q? Integrate both natural capital and built capital to estimate resource use efficiency

Q? If water is scarce, what soils might be irrigated to maximise soil services? and how could land uses/mitigations best be distributed across soils?

Review of the distribution, land use, and research knowledge of stony soils. Sam Carrick

Drainage behaviour of stony soils

Sam Carrick
Jagath Ekanayake
Trevor Webb

New vadose zone sampler

3 sites tested

Young sandy gravels
- Omakau and Hawea Flat
Purpose: Pivot effluent application efficiency

Moderate claybound gravels
- Lincoln
Purpose: Test prototype collection efficiency

Results

- Young sandy gravels 90-120% collection efficiency (=irrigator application variability)
- Clayey gravels 80% efficiency
- Clayey gravels field capacity = -2 to -3kPa
= Do we know PAW for stony soils ?

Next....

From urine patch paper need a **long line** for good representative interception sample

1. 20 m Pipe lysimeter – giant suction cup (but continuous suction)
Minimum target = concentration sampler, use lysimeters to get flux
2. Channel lysimeter mkII
 - Apply suction for clayey gravels
 - Big increase in length and area

Systems research for sustainable South Island dairy farming. Ina Pinxterhuis

Systems research for sustainable South Island dairy farming

Ina Pinxterhuis
Soils Research and Irrigation in Canterbury - Regional Workshop 1 March 2012

DairyNZ – applied research

- Applied research
 - Co-development with farmers
 - Focus on farm systems
- = mix of science and extension

How to combine more milk with low emissions and high animal welfare? Three examples: Pastoral 21 farmlets, Southern Wintering Systems and Co-learning nutrient management

Pastoral 21 - Canterbury Next generation dairy systems

Comparing two management strategies:

- **HSE**
5.0 cows/ha, high genetic merit cows, 400 kg N/ha/year, DCD, 800 kg concentrates/cow/year, wintering on fodder beet
- **LSE**
3.5 cows/ha, higher genetic merit cows, 150 kg N/ha/year, DCD, 100 kg concentrates/cow/year, diverse pastures, wintering on kale in rotation with cereal crop for whole crop silage

Southern Wintering Systems

Good example of co-development

- 4 year programme
- 6 commercial farms
- Range of wintering systems
- Whole farm system analysis
- Detailed monitoring and development of tools and key performance indicators

Nutrient management

- Co-learning proposal still in development phase
- Monitoring new conversion, with two different soil management approaches: “conventional” and “biological”; both under irrigation management, decision making, farm performance (pasture production and quality, milk solid production, animal health, financials, soil quality)

- Should be part of framework South Island Nutrient Management

Systems research for sustainable South Island dairy farming:

Co-development means input and ideas for collaboration are greatly appreciated

The effect of irrigation system and soil type on crop production and water requirements. Hamish Brown

'Experimental' Setup

Experiments conducted *in silico*

- Using: APSIM farm system model
- Simulating: Wheat → Greenfeed → Kale → Barley
- Under: 2030 A2 climate (NIWA)
- With: Roto-rainer or Centre Pivot irrigator
- On: High or Low AWC soils

Irrigation Requirement

Crop Yields

Crop Yields

How the new S-map soil database can help with irrigation modelling. Trevor Webb

S-map data and irrigation

S-map a system to quantify soil spatial variability

Functional Horizon Descriptors

Stone content	Texture of fines	Structure size	Consistence
Non-stony Stony (S)	Sandy (A) Loamy (L)	Coarse (C) Fine (F)	Weak (w) Slightly firm (s) Firm (f)
Very stony (V) Extremely stony (X)	Clayey (Y)		Loose (l) Compact (c) Dense (d)

TLFs = topsoil (t), non-stony, loamy (L), fine structure (F), slightly firm (s)
 SYCf = subsoil, stony (S), clayey (Y), coarse structure (C), firm (f)
 VAc = subsoil, very stony (V), sandy (A), compact (c)

Example map units in S-map

The changes in soils observed on farms over the past 40 years of irrigation. Bob Engelbrecht

Oral only presentation.

Soils in the New Zealand Landscape – the Living Mantle, 2nd Edition

Soils in the New Zealand Landscape – the Living Mantle, 2nd Edition, by Les Molloy, is an outstanding book on New Zealand soils and the agriculture and landscapes they underlie.

This book is superbly illustrated with colour photographs, and is a classic work on New Zealand soils. An essential companion for all who are interested in the use, conservation and science of our soil resource. Hard copies can be found online.

Scanned pdf version available from
<https://nzsss.science.org.nz/books/>

Modelling cumulative effects of land intensification. Linda Lilburne

Modelling cumulative effects of land intensification in Canterbury

Linda Lilburne and ~50 others!

Land use mapping

Multi year summary

Irrigation mapping

ECan analysis = blue. This study = green. Both = teal
Comparison with Environment Canterbury analysis of water extraction consents shows significant differences.

Modelling

- Nitrate source
 - Overseer
 - Spasmo
 - Ancestors of Apsim
- Transport
 - CLUES
 - AquiferSim
 - Simple bucket model

CWMS - Different scenarios

Selwyn catchment

Current work

- Assessing water quality state (current and desired)
- Setting catchment limits
- Determining current load
- Allocation of this load
- Setting a Nutrient Discharge Allowance

Some vexing practical shortcomings in soil and water wrt irrigation. Tony Davoren

Some vexing practical shortcomings in soil and water wrt irrigation

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

Irrigation in shoulder seasons

Key Issues:

- Why do pastoral irrigators persist with irrigation in shoulder seasons when soil temperature is the driving force

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

Getting Soil Moisture Parameters Right

Laboratory v Field Measurements

- Find field (*in situ*) measurements of soil moisture and resulting field capacity and wilting point vary from some (not all) laboratory equivalents
- Field measurements based on field derived soil retention curves

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

van Genuchten curves fitted

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

Changes in Soil Moisture?

Claims that land use has increased whc

- How?
- True and real?
- In life time can't change the texture
- Changes in organic matter content not large enough to increase whc
- Is it just structural improvement?
- Is it just improved infiltration?

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

MEASURING SOIL MOISTURE

Some Basic Requirements:

- Many Depths
- Many Sites
- Continuous Depths
- Volumetric (% or mm) answer

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

How Many Measurements?

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

HOW DEEP?

On-site, accurate irrigation management to meet your specific crop requirements

What is 'Good Management Practice' for irrigation? Paul Reese

Good Management Practice

For irrigators there are two parts to achieving Good Management Practice:

1. Getting your irrigation right - **Water use efficiency**
2. Getting your nutrients right - **Nutrient use efficiency**

INZ framework to cost effectively achieve & demonstrate Water Use Efficiency

Based on Codes of Practice and Standards – 10 years of investment Consistently applied by regulators and industry throughout NZ

Key points

1. an irrigation system that is able to apply water efficiently
2. management that ensures actual use of water is efficient

GMP - Water Use Efficiency

GMP – Nutrient Use Efficiency

Industry

Nutrient use efficiency pathways being worked through

On farm

- Nutrient **risk management** plans
Identify high risk areas and practices that cause high nutrient loss.
- An corresponding **action plan – auditable**
Show how you manage your farm system to minimise nutrient losses

Irrigation Scheme Environmental Management System process & template available on website

Irrigation research

We need a structured approach to R & D - Across sectors

- work out what is needed
- what are the issues we have to tackle
- prioritise them
- how are we going to deal with them
- how can the various organisations coordinate and collectively tackle the issues by breaking them down into manageable modules and tackle according to their expertise
- Who is going to coordinate

Improving the efficiency of the allocation and use of irrigation water. John Bright

Improving Water Allocation to, and Efficiency of, Irrigation

John Bright, Aqualinc
Jenna Donaggio, Aqualinc
Joe Powers, Aqualinc
Graeme Buchan, Lincoln University

GROUNDWATER | IRRIGATION | RESOURCE CONSERVATION | LAND USE IMPACTS | WASTE TREATMENT | WATER MANAGEMENT

March 1, 2012 Presenter / Jenna Donaggio

Water Allocation for Irrigation

- Annual Irrigation Water Use
 - What is reasonable usage by an efficient operator?
- Knowledge of actual evapotranspiration required to answer this question

March 1, 2012 AQUALINC

ET_o, ET_p and ET_a

- ET_o calculation from climate data assumes hypothetical reference grass crop with a set height (0.12 m), surface resistance (70 s m⁻¹), and albedo of 0.23.
- ET_p can be related to ET_o by way of a crop coefficient (K_c):

$$ET_p = K_c ET_o$$
- Crop coefficient reflects differences in crop height, albedo, canopy resistance and evaporation from the soil of a specific crop under standard conditions (i.e. crop is well watered).
- Actual evapotranspiration, ET_a, calculated from ET_p using a stress coefficient.

$$ET_a = K_s ET_p$$

March 1, 2012 AQUALINC

Measurement of ET_a

- ET_a (ET_p when water non-limiting) can be calculated using the water balance approach, in which necessary data is obtained from field measurements

Soil water balance of the root zone (Source: Allen et al., 1998)

$$ET_a = R_{(t_2-t_1)} + I_{(t_2-t_1)} - D_{(t_2-t_1)} - (S_{t_2} - S_{t_1})$$

March 1, 2012 AQUALINC

Research Objectives

- Develop a crop coefficient (ET_p / ET_o) time series for pasture, based on climate, irrigation, drainage and soil water content data collected from 4 lysimeter sites across Canterbury over a 24 month period.
- Quantify temporal variations in pasture canopy characteristics
- Examine the relationship between temporal variations in actual evapotranspiration and pasture canopy characteristics

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Initial results

March 1, 2012

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Understanding the effects of irrigation application intensity on application efficiency

March 1, 2012

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Understanding the effects of irrigation application intensity on application efficiency

- Measure the effects of irrigation intensity and application depth on application efficiency.
- Lysimeter-based experimental programme using LU facilities. Follows on from some field work conducted under centre-pivots for Dairy NZ.
- Experiments completed. Data analysis well advanced. Some unexpected results...!

March 1, 2012

AQUALINC

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Thank you for listening

GROUNDWATER IRRIGATION RESOURCE CONSERVATION LAND USE IMPACTS WASTE TREATMENT WATER MANAGEMENT

March 1, 2012

Presenter / Jenna Donaggio

Precision irrigation scheduling using wireless soil sensor networks. Carolyn Hedley

PRECISION IRRIGATION SCHEDULING USING WIRELESS SOIL MOISTURE SENSOR NETWORKS

Carolyn Hedley, Jagath Ekanayake, Pierre Roudier

(1) Mapping soil moisture status

(2) VRI modification of the pivot

Landcare Research
Manaaki Whenua

PRECISION
irrigation

(3) Soil moisture monitoring - web-enabled wireless sensor networks

The image shows a computer monitor displaying a web-based interface for monitoring soil moisture. The interface includes a map of the field with sensor locations, a list of sensor data, and a graph showing soil moisture levels over time. A photograph of a sensor node in a field is shown next to the interface. A diagram illustrates the connection between the sensor nodes, a base station, and the Internet.

WSN monitors:

- Volumetric soil moisture
- Soil water tension
- Height of water table
- Rainfall
- Soil temperature
- Drainage events

(4) Precision irrigation scheduling - web-enabled wireless sensor networks

ZONE	Depth	0kPa	5kPa	10kPa	50kPa	100kPa	1500kPa	AWC	RAW
		% v/v						mm/m	
1_DRY	0-20	52	25	16	12	10	4	120	70

The screenshot shows a web-based interface for precision irrigation scheduling. It features a graph with multiple lines representing different soil moisture sensors over time, from November 2011 to January 2012. The graph shows fluctuations in soil moisture levels, with peaks and troughs. The interface includes various controls and options for data analysis and reporting.

(5) Customised VRI software (www.precisionirrigation.co.nz)

Summary

- Measure soil variability – using EM, DEM and yield maps
- Monitor soil moisture status in management zones – web-enabled wireless sensor networks
- Provides the ability for precision management
- Trials-to-date show water savings of up to 40%, improved IWUE, reduced drainage and runoff, minimised nutrient leakage, flexibility, improved soil condition, return on investment in 1-5 years.

Landcare Research
Manaaki Whenua

Pasture yield mapping to inform management. Samuel Dennis

YIELD MAPPING TO INFORM IRRIGATION

Samuel Dennis
 Robyn Dynes
 Todd White
 Karren O'Neill
 Carolyn Hedley
 Ian Yule
 Westlea Clarke-Hill

www.sff.govt.nz

agresearch

agresearch Farm 1: Height over position

SUMMARY

- Spatial yield mapping can identify production limitations due to irrigation
 - Inadequate water application
 - High intensity -> reduced yield
- Pursuing funding to more fully investigate potential application of yield mapping

agresearch

Quantifying water demand and irrigation response of arable and forage crops.

Andrew Fletcher

The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited

Plant & Food
RESEARCH
RANGAHAU AHUMARA KAI

Quantifying water demand and irrigation response of arable and forage crops

Andrew Fletcher

February 2012

Background

- Aims of our research:
 - For a range of crops understand the processes of:
 - crop demand for water
 - soil water supply and extraction patterns
 - yield response to drought.
 - In order to deliver improved irrigation practices that:
 - Maintain production
 - And minimise water use
- Much of the research is funded by the Land Use Change & Intensification program

Rain-out shelter

- Eliminate rainfall
- All water supplied by drip irrigation
- Setup a range of drought treatments
 - Intensities
 - Timings
- 4 bays
- Cropping rotation

year	crop
87_88	potatoes
88_89	barley
89_90	peas
90_91	maize
91_92	wheat
92_93	peas
93_94	wheat
94_95	potatoes
95_96	barley
96_97	sweet corn
97_98	peas
98_99	oats
99_00	carrots
00_01	grass seed
01_02	clover
02_03	grass seed
03_04	peas
04_05	peas
05_07	pasture
07_08	Turnips/rape
11_12	soya

Plot set-up / Measurements

Crop measurements

Soil measurements

Critical deficits

Rooting depth of forage brassicas

Water use efficiency of forage brassicas

Current / Future work

- Current
 - Kale: Drought stress and N fertility
- Next season
 - Silage maize: Drought stress and N fertility
- Following season
 - Range of cereal crops: are some crops better under drought

Checking irrigation reality. Channa Rajanayaka

Checking Irrigation Reality

Channa Rajanayaka

GROUNDWATER IRRIGATION RESOURCE CONSERVATION LAND USE IMPACTS WASTE TREATMENT WATER MANAGEMENT

March 1, 2012 Presenter: Channa

Available Soil Water

Source: DairyNZ

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Field Monitoring

- To better understand irrigation management in the field, Aqualinc has been monitoring water contents through the soil profile.
- Three-year field investigation:
 - 4 vegetable
 - 2 pasture

Monitoring sites

March 1, 2012

Water content

- Determines volumetric water content (VWC) by measuring soil dielectric constant
- Continuous recording using 5 sensors in each soil profile to approx. 800 mm depth

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Irrigation and Rainfall

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Measurements - Centre Pivot

Travelling Gun / Vegetable

Travelling Gun / Vegetable (2)

Irrigation vs Productivity

- Lack of monitoring prevents the actual field irrigation management practices achieving optimum productions.

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Evaluation of methods to sample nitrate leaching from grazed pasture. Linda Lilburne

Evaluation of methods to sample nitrate leaching from grazed pasture

Linda Lilburne, Sam Carrick, Trevor Webb, Jim Moir

Sampling urine patches

- Adequate sampling of urine patches

Histogram of 100 suction cup leaching measurements

Variability in estimates

Percentage of estimates of nitrate leached with an error more than +/- 20% of true value

Conclusion

- Impractical with current technology to adequately measure nitrate leached under grazed pasture
- Better approach is to run controlled experiments
- Use results to
 - calibrate models
 - extrapolate up for paddock estimate.

Transport of Br and microbes through intact cores of alluvial gravel vadose zone material. Murray Close

ESR

Transport of Br and Microbes through intact cores of alluvial gravel vadose zone material

Murray Close

Specialist Science Solutions
 Manaaki Tangata Tairā Haki
 protecting people and their environment through science
 www.esr.cri.nz

Alluvial gravel aquifer

- Three main textures
- Sandy gravel
 - Sand
 - Open frameworks
 - Coated (Fe, Mn)
 - Non-coated

© ESR 2010

Undisturbed vadose zone cores

diameter: 30 cm diameter: 50 cm
 height: 40 cm height: 60-70 cm

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Intact core collection

ESR

© ESR 2010

Intact core collection

ESR

Experimental Setup

© ESR 2010

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Experimental set-up for unsaturated flow experiments

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Saturated flow – K~3-20 m/day

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Flow = ~8-9 mm/hr

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Flow = 0.5 mm/hr

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Summary of unsaturated flow experiments

Flow conditions for experiment	% Macropore	Microbe recovery (%)	Hydraulic conductivity-K (m/day)
Saturated flow	0.80	E. coli: 60	4
8 mm/hr	0.60	E. coli: 0.005 Phage: 1.3	0.19
0.5 to 0.8 mm/hr	0.67	E. coli: 0.0003 Phage: 0.000006	0.016
0.4 mm/hr (2 stage)	0.36		0.008

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Impact of contrasting irrigation frequencies on ryegrass and lucerne yields on shallow soils. Edmar Teixeira

The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited

Plant & Food RESEARCH
RANGAHAU AHUMĀRA KAI

Irrigation frequency impacts on pastures grown in shallow soils

Edmar Teixeira, Hamish Brown, Andrew Fletcher, Mike George, Shane Maley, Richard Gillespie, Richard Hubber, Alex Michel, Esther Menken.... and others ...

Purpose of the field experiment

AIMS:
 "Improve efficiency of irrigation ...
 ... for 2 pasture crops with contrasting root systems ...
 ... on drought-prone soils ...
 ... through better quantitative understanding of soil and plant processes"

OBJECTIVES:
 Quantify:

- Yield responses
- Water availability (Supply side)
- Plant uptake (Demand side)
- Stress thresholds and mechanisms

Agronomy } Modelling } Physiology

The New Zealand Institute for Plant & Food Research Limited

Treatments:

- (1) each 3-4 days
- (2) each 7 days
- (3) each 14 days
- (4) No Irrigation

Amount:
100% ET - rainfall

way to mimic irrigator types ...

Pastures with different root systems

Lucerne
Ryegrass

Moisture monitoring

Neutron Probe "2 weeks"

Automated TDRs "hourly"

0.15 m
0.30 m
1.50 m

Finding the daily rate of water uptake "k" parameter (modelling side)

Soil Water (%)

time

Root front arrival

E: Evaporation
T: Transpiration

high k_I
low k_I

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What else are we measuring?

Site Weather
&
Canopy Temperature

Biomass
Canopy cover
Yield Components ...

Treatment effects so far ...

Lucerne

Ryegrass

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Example of soil water dynamics so far (Lucerne 0-15 cm)

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Foz do Iguaçu – South of Brazil

Experimental lay-out in L&P

17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
Ryegrass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Lucerne	Ryegrass	Lucerne	Ryegrass	Ryegrass	Ryegrass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Lucerne	Ryegrass	Lucerne	Ryegrass	Ryegrass
Irr(2)	Irr(3)	Irr(1)	Dry	Irr(1)	Irr(2)	Irr(3)	Dry	Irr(1)	Irr(1)	Irr(3)	Irr(2)	Dry	Dry	Dry	Irr(2)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Ryegrass	Ryegrass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Ryegrass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Ryegrass	Ryegrass	Ryegrass	Lucerne	Ryegrass	Lucerne	Lucerne	Lucerne	Ryegrass
Irr(2)	Dry	Dry	Irr(3)	Irr(3)	Irr(2)	Irr(1)	Irr(1)	Irr(1)	Irr(1)	Dry	Irr(3)	Irr(3)	Dry	Irr(2)	Irr(2)
Pasture Species		Irrigation Treatments													
1	2	Full irrigation TRICE & wean													
3	4	Full irrigation CRICE & wean													
5	6	Full irrigation RPTHEIGSRTLY													
7	8	Full irrigation (drywean)													
9	10	Full irrigation (drywean)													
11	12	Full irrigation (drywean)													
13	14	Full irrigation (drywean)													
15	16	Full irrigation (drywean)													

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Session III - Do we understand the soil processes to allow sustainable land management under irrigation?

Minimising water contamination by microbial transport from land-applied wastes. Graeme Buchan

Minimising water contamination by microbial transport from land-applied wastes

Collaborative research between:

- Graeme Buchan, Soil & Physical Sciences Dept, LU
 - ESR Christchurch (Liping Pang, Murray Close)
 - Shuang Jiang (PhD student)
- plus other research by
- Keith Cameron (CSER)
 - Sam Carrick, Landcare Research

LU has:
Extensive research into N and P transfer to water resources.
This research is complementary, adding in the microbes

Investigating BASIC MECHANISMS

Transport and trapping of bacteria in soil columns ('lysimeters')

Effects on bacterial leaching of flood vs. sprinkler irrigation

- **Flood irrigation** (extreme):
100 mm on a 14-day cycle, as a 'worst case'
- **Spray irrigation** (intermediate):
50 mm on a 14-day cycle

We used SIX replicate columns (Templeton soil)

Result 1

Effect of irrigation method

- **Flood irrigation** gave greater leaching volumes
- Bacterial concentrations in leachate were typically **ten times higher** under flood than spray irrigation

Result 2

Effect of Season

- The 'seasonal condition' of the soil influenced bacterial leaching - less risk of leaching in autumn than in summer
- probably due to more shrinkage cracks during summer drying

General Conclusions

- **Under right conditions**, soil can filter microbes, even under intensive agriculture
- **Effect of soil wetness**: Even low suction gave 1 to 2 log reduction in bacterial breakthrough

Recommendations for Practice

To reduce risks of water contamination by microbes.....

1. *Avoid saturated soil and deeply connected macro-pore flow*

Even slight de-saturation will empty largest pores and break pore connectivity

2. **Irrigation system**

Spray is better than flood irrigation.

Yes – and I get a free shower

3. **Seasonal effect**

Macro-pore flow is more likely during summer, when soils may crack

4. **Use irrigation scheduling !!!**

Monitor soil water, to avoid

- a) excessive irrigation
- or
- b) soils getting extremely dry & cracking in summer

Soil moisture probes

A restaurant offering free microbial contamination

Microbial leaching through stony soils following dairy shed effluent application.

Malcolm McLeod

Microbial leaching through stony soils following dairy shed effluent application

Malcolm McLeod, Jackie Aislabie
Alexandra McGill, Phillippa Rhodes,
Sam Carrick, Grant Northcott

Background

- In mid- to north Canterbury 73% of dairy farms are on stony soils with <400 mm of fines over gravel.
- Expansion of dairying is ongoing, with areas such as the MacKenzie basin seen as potential areas for conversion to dairy farming.
- Irrigation of dairy shed effluent onto land is an integral part of New Zealand's farming practice.

Question

- Are some of the stony soils "leaky" to DSE applied to the soil surface?

Experimental

- Collected MacKenzie soil barrel lysimeters
 - Gravels to surface, 4 reps
 - 30 cm fines over gravels, 4 reps
 - 60 cm fines over gravels, 4 reps
- Applied 25 mm DSE followed by rainfall
 - Both 5 mm/h
- Analysed each litre of leachate for *E. coli*
 - To 1 PV = 44 L

Results to 1 Pore Volume = 44L

Soil	<i>E. coli</i> in applied DSE (per 100 mL)	<i>E. coli</i> in leachate (per 100 mL)
Gravels to surface	4.1×10^6	1 - 9
30 cm fines over gravels	2.0×10^6	1 - 258 3.1×10^5
60 cm fines over gravels	6.3×10^6	1 - 248
Control	0	0

Guideline level of 550 *E. coli*/100 mL for freshwater, indicates an unacceptable public health risk for microbiological contamination

Takeaway

- Levels of the microbial indicator *Escherichia coli* in soil leachates were typically low, except for one core
- We anticipate that the bypass flow characteristics of these soils could be vulnerable to land management practices, particularly under irrigated intensive dairying

Microbial transport from dairying under different irrigation systems – flood, centre pivot and travelling irrigator. Murray Close

ESR

Microbial transport from dairying under different irrigation systems in Canterbury

Murray Close
Principal Scientist, ESR

Specialist Science Solutions
Manaaki Tangata Tāiao Hoki
protecting people and their environment through science

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ESR

Background

- Large increase in dairying combined with the use of irrigation over past 10-15 years in NZ
- Needed to know if dairying with irrigation was having an impact on microbial groundwater quality
- A study looking at border strip (flood) irrigation and dairying
 - Close et al. (2008). Microbial groundwater quality and its health implications for a border-strip irrigated dairy farm catchment, South Island, New Zealand. *J. of Water & Health* 6(1): 83–98.
- A study looking at microbial transport from dairying with two spray irrigation systems – centre pivot & travelling irrigator
 - Close et al. (2010). Microbial transport from Dairying under two Spray Irrigation systems in Canterbury, New Zealand. *J. of Environmental Quality* 39(3): 824-833.

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ESR

Flood irrigation with Dairying

- *E. coli* & *Campylobacter* were sampled in shallow wells in Waikakahi catchment over 3 years
- Well selection excluded other sources
- *E. coli* found in 75% of samples
 - Levels ranging from <1 to 2400 MPN/100ml
- *Campylobacter* found in 12% of samples
 - levels range from <0.6 to >3.1 MPN/L
- More contamination during irrigation season

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ESR

Flood irrigation with Dairying

- Carried out assessment of health risk
- Combined concentrations found in groundwater with dose response curve
- Probability of infection during irrigation season = 60 - 75%
- Sickness is probably 30 - 50% of infection rate so about 20 - 35%
- Looked at EpiSurv notifications of enteric disease in similar areas (9 years data: 1997-2005)
- Results indicate significantly higher levels of Campylobacteriosis, Cryptosporidiosis & Salmonellosis in areas of flood irrigation with dairying

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Methodology - Centre Pivot

- Centre Pivot applies water every 3-4 days with about 10-18 mm per application
- Lincoln University Dairy farm - converted in 2001.
- Groundwater table at 8-10 m bgl
- Installed 6 up-gradient and 8 down-gradient monitoring wells in shallow groundwater
- Monitored monthly for 6 years
- Water samples analysed for faecal coliforms and *Campylobacter* (p/a)

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Lincoln Dairy Farm

Methodology – Travelling Irrigator Briggs RotaRainer

- Dairy farm in South Canterbury
- Briggs RotaRainer applies water every 14 days with about 50-60 mm per application
- Took samples using the Lincoln Ventures Linear Lysimeter- collects free-draining leachate @ 1.5 m
- Lysimeter divided into 1 m² cells
- Collected leachate samples over 4 year period from 10 cells
- Samples analysed for faecal coliforms and *Campylobacter*

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Results - Briggs RotaRainer

- Rainfall (9 sampling rounds), mean = 28 mm
 - Very low coliforms; no Campy
- Irrigation (7 sampling rounds), mean = 55 mm
 - Some coliforms, no Campy
- High rate irrigation: irrigation plus heavy rain, (4 sampling rounds), mean = 80 mm
 - Lots of coliforms, no Campy
 - No fresh cow pats

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Overall Conclusions

- Little leaching of bacteria with rain or spray irrigation at depths of 55 mm
- More leaching of faecal coliforms at 80 mm application depths
- No detection of *Campylobacter* for 80 mm application depths without cow pats
- Some detection of *Campylobacter* and tracer bacteria for 80 mm application depths with fresh cow pats
- Little, if any, impact of Centre Pivot system on microbial groundwater quality with groundwater @ 9 m and good management practices

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Results :Centre Pivot

- Faecal coliforms
 - Upgradient wells = 5.4%
 - Down-gradient wells = 2.8%
- *Campylobacter*
 - Upgradient wells = 0.7%
 - Down-gradient wells = 0.7%
- No difference between up-gradient & down-gradient detections of microbes
- Little, if any, impact on microbial quality of groundwater from Centre Pivot irrigation system with groundwater @ 9 m and good management

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Irrigation of spiked cow pats

- Placed fresh cow pats on half lysimeter cells & spiked with a tracer bacteria
- Irrigated with 80 mm 2 days later
- Most cells with cow pats showed low levels of *Campy* as well as coliforms & tracer at 1.5 m depth
- Detection of *B. subtilis* tracer indicates that the bacteria had leached from the cow pats
- Some transport of microbes if irrigation is combined with heavy rainfall & cow pats are fresh

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Overall Conclusions

- In contrast to the spray irrigation systems, under border strip irrigation there are significant levels of *E. coli* and *Campylobacter* in shallow groundwater
- There is a significant risk for drinking this water and there is a significant increase in disease notifications for this land use practice
- We have recommended that border strip areas convert to spray irrigation

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Drainage and leaching losses under different irrigation systems. Trish Fraser

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Plant & Food RESEARCH
RANGAHAU AHUMĀRA KAI

Drainage and leaching losses under different irrigation systems

Prepared by: Trish Fraser (Plant & Food Research)
Samuel Dennis (AgResearch)
Sam Carrick (Landcare Research)

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Background

- Intent of irrigation systems
= apply water uniformly
- In practice
= depth and intensity of application vary
- Result
= potential drainage and leaching; soil dependent
- Research priority
= establish a lysimeter facility;
simulate irrigation systems on lysimeters;
better quantify drainage and leaching losses
from a range of soil types

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Background

- Models commonly use a water balance calculation to estimate drainage
- Improved validation of drainage (and leaching) estimates under different rates of irrigation/ different soil types is required to refine current model predictions
- Current research project team
 - Plant & Food Research (Trish Fraser)
 - AgResearch (Samuel Dennis)
 - Landcare Research (Sam Carrick)

In collaboration with

- Lincoln University (Keith Cameron and Di Hong-Jie)

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Lysimeter facility planned

- Plans to build a new lysimeter facility
- Retractable rainshelter

Lincoln University Lysimeters

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Lysimeter facility planned

- Characterise under controlled water input conditions:
 - water and solute storage/ movement attributes for modellers
 - how contrasting soils behave under different irrigation rates

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Glasshouse experiment – in the interim

Glasshouse experiment

Glasshouse experiments

- 2 soil types – Templeton and Darnley (extracted adjacent to ECan field lysimeter sites)
- Controlled water inputs
- Initially characterise water storage and movement under a range of simulated irrigation water intensities
- Later also plan to investigate solute storage/movement attributes (particularly nitrogen)
- Characterisation of how two contrasting soils behave under different irrigation rates
- Experimental set up nearly ready to run first series of experiments on these lysimeters...

Preliminary results from irrigated drainage lysimeters in Canterbury. MS Srivanasan

Taihoro Nukurangi

Groundwater Recharge Under Irrigated Agriculture – Preliminary Results From The Canterbury Lysimeter Network

Maurice Duncan, NIWA
MS Srinivasan, NIWA

NZ Society Soil Science, Lincoln, March 2012

Taihoro Nukurangi

The issues:

- Little is known about ground-water recharge under irrigation in Canterbury
- There are concerns about:
 - Increasing demand for groundwater
 - The sustainability of current extraction rates
 - The quality and quantity of ground-water sources for lowland streams

Taihoro Nukurangi

ECan initiative

- ECan consulted with CRI's, Agribusiness and farmers as how best fill the knowledge gap
- One solution: a network of drainage lysimeters sampling the range of climates, soils and land covers in Canterbury
- Participants: ECan, NIWA, Aqualinc, HydroServices and farmers

Taihoro Nukurangi

Lysimeter sites:

- West Eyreton**
Rain ~550 mm/y, shallow stony soils, dairy
- Methven**
Rain ~900 mm/y, shallow stony soils, dairy
- Dorie**
Rain ~550 mm/y, deep silt loam, dairy
- Wakanui**
Rain ~550 mm/y, deep silt loam, cropping.

Taihoro Nukurangi

Lysimeter sites

- **Equipment:**
 - Lysimeters are 0.5 m diameter and 0.7 m deep – most are fitted with wicks
 - 3 lysimeters/site, each with a tipping bucket
 - 3 soil moisture sensors / site
 - Neutron probe soil moisture in each lysimeter
 - Ground-level raingauge – rain and irrigation
 - Compact weather station - rain
 - 2 sites have eddy covariance towers to independently sample evapotranspiration

Taihoro Nukurangi

Monthly summary

Rainfall + irrigation 910 mm/y
Drainage 116 mm/y

Most drainage happens outside the irrigation season

That's all folks

Thanks for your attention

Measurement, modelling and mitigation of nitrate leaching in arable and forage cropping systems. Mike Beare

Measurement, modelling and mitigation of nitrate leaching in rainfed and irrigated cropping systems

M Beare, S Thomas, T Fraser, J Sharp and many Sustainable Production colleagues

Soil Research and Irrigation in Canterbury - workshop
Lincoln (1 March 2012)

Quantifying losses under field conditions

Measurement methods

- Soil solution sampling (60 & 150 cm depths)
- Drainage calculated using water balance model

Arable crop systems

- Tillage & crop rotation effects on leaching losses
- Can optimize irrigation mgt to differences in soil water relations (storage, conductivity, WUE)?
- How do effects of soil compaction on soil water relations affect risk of losses (leaching & gaseous emissions)?

Vegetable crop systems

- Interactions b/w irrigation and N fertiliser mgt?
- Crop sequences to avoid extended fallow periods

Forage crop systems

- Is 45 t/ha of forage DM & a 50% reduction in N leaching losses achievable?
- Can we combine reduced tillage with early or late grazing of crops to minimise the risk of losses?
- Can crops mop up excess N in effluent/irrigated soils and do we optimise irrigation mgt to max. uptake & minimise losses?

Critical factors, metrics and mitigation options

Management effects and mitigation options

- Benefits of winter cover crops well established
- No-tillage may ↑ NO₃ losses at high winter rainfall
 - Can irrigation be managed to reduce this risk?
- Critical to match irrigation AND N fertiliser to crop demand
- Losses from grazed forage crops >> cut & carry crops
- Deep root crops can reduce risk of losses from effluent/irrigated soils

Important soil and environmental factors

- Winter rainfall is a key driver of winter leaching losses
- Autumn mineral N and stored water are also significant factors. Are they practically significant?
- Does reducing soil water deficit with irrigation increase risk of leaching losses? Is there a critical point to balance the economic and environmental trade-off?

Metrics for eco-verifying proposed mitigation options

- Net losses (kg N/ha) vs intensity of losses
 - Kg NO₃ leached / t DM produced
 - Kg N leached / \$ gross margin
- Can we derive Emission Factors for NO₃ leaching (as for N₂O)?
 - N leached / kg fertiliser N applied
 - N leached / mm irrigation applied

Crop Sequence	Total DM (t/ha)	NO ₃ leached per t DM
Barley/Rape/Oats	24.0	1.8
Barley/Oats/Pyrgrass	28.1	0.9
Kaie/Wheat	24.8	3.2
Kaie/Triticale-bean	26.1	1.5
Maize/Wheat	30.0	2.4
Maize/Triticale-bean	32.5	2.4

Modelling leaching losses with APSIM

Growing need to use models to:

- Predict management effects on N dynamics and associated environmental losses
- Identify mitigation options that sustain high levels of production and resource use efficiency

Few soil models incorporate the complexities of soil – plant – management interactions.

- Systems models (eg APSIM) are one approach

APSIM crop modules have undergone extensive testing, but soil modules haven't, especially under New Zealand conditions

Programme of testing APSIM against existing datasets including

- Millennium tillage trial
- Intensive cropping trials
- Laboratory experiments
- Rothamsted long-term trials

Thank You

Acknowledgements: A host of colleagues in the Sustainable Production portfolio at PFR for scientific and technical support. Research was funded by the *Land Use Change and Intensification* (PFR Core) and *Pasture 21* Programmes

Influence of cattle compaction on water storage dynamics in a rolling downlands soil. Seth Laurenson

Influence of cattle compaction on water storage dynamics in a rolling downland soil

LUCI Project Seth Laurenson, Dave Houlbrooke

NORD Land Use Intensification= more grass, more cows.

agresearch

Grazing at high moisture content
Increased stocking density
= DECREASED MACROPOROSITY

Change in pore size distribution under cattle grazing

- 1) Macro → Micro pores
- 2) Overall decline in porosity

Changes in Water Storage

Water Holding Capacity decreases in Compacted Soils

Increased risk of run-off at high moisture content
Increased compaction risk if recovery period restricted by prolonged wet conditions

Changes in Surface run-off under rainfall

Driven primarily by saturation excess conditions.

Soil-water balance used to predict 'excess water' at 5 locations on the slope

NIWA Rainfall data 2010/11

Increased run-off greatest from shallow upper slope profiles following compaction

agresearch

Avoiding on-going effects of soil compaction

Using a soil moisture content (SWD) as a decision tool for grazing as well as irrigation

- Avoid compaction by strategic grazing, particularly on fragile shallow soils.
- Delay grazing following irrigation event till $\theta_v < \text{CMC}$.
- Cycles of natural recovery do occur but the time frame will be longer for more severely damaged soils.
- On-going grazing can lead to a progressive decline in soil structure if the recovery period > grazing rotation.

Soil, water and nitrogen transformation in agricultural soils. Steve Thomas

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Prepared by:
Steve Thomas, Tina Harrison-Kirk, Mike Beare (Plant & Food Research)
Tony van der Weerden (Agriculture Research Centre)
And many others!

Soil water = key driver of N transformations and N₂O emissions

Water content (and soil physical conditions) influence:
*O₂ content of soil pores
*regulates O₂ and N₂O gas diffusion

Largest emissions typically from denitrification – saturated soils and anaerobic conditions.

Opportunity to use knowledge of the relationship between soil water, soil physical conditions and N₂O emissions to guide:

- *grazing timing/intensity
 - *manure & fertiliser applications
 - *manage tillage
 - *manage irrigation/drainage
- to reduce risk of large N₂O emissions

(after Granli and Brockman 1994)

Compaction, soil water and N₂O emissions in field conditions?

Effects of tractor compaction on N₂O emissions from irrigated potatoes:

- Emissions occurred after rain/irrigation
- Unfertilised compacted furrow > fertilised ridge > uncompacted furrow
- Minimising compaction to reduce emissions.

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Compaction, soil water and N₂O emissions in field conditions?

Effects of tillage and simulated grazing timing (soil moisture content) on N₂O emissions:

Compaction from grazing:
↑ N₂O emissions
↓ DM production

- Establish forages with minimal soil disturbance
- Avoid grazing when soil ≥ FC
- Direct drill to mitigate N₂O emissions

Thomas et al. 2008 Plant Soil 309:131-145

Compaction, soil water/aeration N transformations and gas emissions from 15N-labelled urine

- "Wet end" - saturation to FC using tension tables
- Horotiu silt loam
- 0, 220 & 400 kPa, produced BDs of 0.83, 0.86 & 0.88 g/cm³.
- Compacted soils = different pore size distribution.

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Dry/wet cycles + compaction affect N₂O emissions

Total N₂O emissions (μg N kg⁻¹ dry soil)

Compaction Treatments	Moisture Trts	Total N ₂ O
Uncompacted	Wet/Wet	1
Uncompacted	Dry/Wet	15
Compacted	Wet/Wet	27
Compacted	Dry/Wet	296
LSD _m (5%)		5.3

Beare et al 2009 SBB 41:611-621

Dry/wet cycles + texture affect N₂O emissions

- Soil texture affects N mineralisation & N₂O emissions
- Drying & rewetting cycles = higher N₂O emissions from fine textured soils.
- Fine-textured soils have a higher proportion of small pores than coarser textured silt loam soils

Treatment ID	Moisture Treatment	Rewet treatment
WW	FC	Maintained at FC
MDW	120% WP	Dry/wet
VDW	80% WP	Dry/wet
MD	120% WP	Maintained dry
VD	80% WP	Maintained dry

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What about N₂O emissions from irrigated soils?

Lack of NZ data!
Lack of international data for irrigated pastures!

- Highest N₂O emissions when soils are wet, warm and high mineral N contents.
- N₂O emissions increase in soils with high proportion of small pores.
- Wetting-drying cycles increase N mineralisation and N₂O emissions – is there an optimum irrigation scheduling strategy?
- Soil compaction increases when soils are wet.

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Best soil water metrics for predicting N₂O emissions on farm?

- Focus on "wet end" – predominantly denitrification.
- Impact of changing soil physical conditions.
- Metric(s) applicable across soil types
- Data through NZAGRC, MSI, P21, MSI funded work.

- Pallic soil (Otokia silt loam)
- Recent soil (Wingatui silt loam)
- MP: 93%
- VWC: 88%
- WFPS: 72%
- RD: 59%

Van der Weerden et al accepted Soil Research

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Oxygen concentration as a function of water content and temperature in tilled versus no-tilled soils. Guillermo Hernandez

Importance

Oxygen concentration in soil air can drive:

- » Root activity and growth, and microbial activity.
- » Chemistry of soil solution.
- » Soil production of greenhouse gases (N₂O).

Oxygen concentration in soil air is driven by:

- » Soil temperature, and soil water content.
- » Oxygen transport from atmosphere to soil and its subsequent consumption by soil organisms and roots.

Hypothesis

In cropped fields, oxygen concentration in soil air following a water input event (e.g., major rainfall or irrigation) depends on the tillage management in place.

Objective

To examine the effects of intensive versus no tillage on oxygen concentration in soil air.

Method

Millennium Tillage Trial site located in Lincoln (2000).

Contrast two adjacent plots:

- » No tillage vs.
- » Intensive tillage: spring & fall tillage using mouldboard ploughed to 20 cm, maxi-till to 10 cm (2), and/or harrow and roll.

Crop: spring barley.

Measurements

Automated, continuous measurements.

Sensors deployed in interrow position at 6 cm soil depth:

- » Soil temperature – thermocouples (n: 6 per experimental plot)
- » Soil water content – TDR (n: 3)
- » Galvanic oxygen sensors – KE-25 (n: 3)

Resolution: 1 minute.

Average: 1 hour.

Results (16 to 29 Dec 2011)

- » Soil temperature
- » Oxygen concentration
- » Soil water content

Soil Temperature and Oxygen

- Temperature pattern are typical.
- Temperature changes explain most of variation in oxygen.
- Lower oxygen in no tillage (~ due to SOC, ρb)

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Soil water and Oxygen

- Soil water follow water input and show wet-drying cycles.
- In the no-tilled soil, water saturation (and drainage) due to rainfall after irrigation cause depletion of oxygen in soil air.

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Summary

- Rapid fluctuations in soil water determined oxygen concentration.
- This response depends on the tillage management in the long-term MTT site.
- Plans for near future for similar measurements at new Forage Trial in conjunction with quantification of greenhouse gases emissions.

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Thanks for the attention

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MANGAWHAI AOTEAROA KM

Discovering & delivering the natural goodness in food

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ANALYSIS OF THE WORKSHOP OUTCOMES

Full text: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1451966>

Executive summary

A one-day workshop, with 58 participants (Appendix) and sponsored by the New Zealand Society of Soil Science, was held at Lincoln on Thursday 1st March 2012.

The aims of the workshop were:

1. To discuss current research and opportunities for future soils research with respect to irrigation in Canterbury
2. To bring soils researchers and industry representatives with irrigation expertise together to enable networking discussions.

During the day there were 27 presentations, each of 5 minutes duration, organised into three themes:

3. How can we tailor irrigation schemes to land/soil resources?
4. Do we have the knowhow to conduct on-farm irrigation sustainably?
5. Do we understand the soil processes to allow sustainable land management under irrigation?

The large number of presentations highlighted that there is a good level of active soil research related to irrigation, across a range of organisations. There is also breadth in this research, ranging from landscape-scale analyses of irrigation schemes, to paddock-scale management technologies, down to processes driving nitrogen and microbe leaching.

Following each presentation theme there was a discussion forum to identify the general state of knowledge, with topics assigned to one of three categories: agreed, debated, and gaps. All results are presented in this report. Overall participants agreed most about the current knowledge status in themes two and three, with considerably less agreement about current knowledge at the landscape scale (theme one). Greatest debate took place within themes one & two, with a lot of research gaps identified across all three themes. Some of the knowledge gaps that were repeatedly identified included:

- There is still a need to better understand the fate of both water and nutrients in the environment.
- Our current knowledge of shallow and stony soils commonly was considered inadequate.
- There is a need for improved understanding of soil physical changes under irrigated conditions.
- Systems modeling was seen as important and a number of opportunities identified, but it was recognised that there were a number of areas where the current models needed to be refined.
- We need to further improve our knowledge of soil water relations (and associated function) to tailor irrigation schemes to specific soil and land resources.
- We need to find ways to improve how we feed science into policy.
- Extension of existing research knowledge was also commonly identified as a general gap.

At the end of the workshop the participants were asked to fill out a survey of current and desired professional interactions, with a social networks analysis of this survey presented at the end of this report. This analysis shows there is a high level of existing professional networking, but only a smaller group that had previously interacted in co-authoring of scientific papers, which probably reflects both the breadth of research disciplines as well as the good turnout of non-scientist participants. Overall, feedback from the participants was very positive and encouraging and all agreed that the aims of the workshop had been met.

One of the most positive outcomes was that there was a high desire for new professional interactions, and participants wanted to see the workshop repeated in the future. We recommend that given the rapid rate of change in Canterbury irrigation that a repeat workshop is held in 1–2 years' time. A worthwhile initiative would be to hold a pan agency collaboration initiative in late 2012 / early 2013 where opportunities for collaborative projects could be identified, prior to the 2013–14 financial year. For the Crown Research agencies, this report should be presented to those involved in the Soil Land Use Alliance (SLUA) initiative, which is aiming to co-ordinate research and funding applications across the different agencies.

